

Proactive Personality a Transformational Leader is Consistent in Maintaining Organizational Balance

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Abstract – The administration of government is closely related to public policy and will be effective if it is accompanied by a healthy bureaucracy. Policymakers at each level have different powers based on their authority. As a result, policymakers' actions in the form of government programs must achieve the goals or objectives. This article describes the interrelationship between the role of bureaucrats and transformational leadership in an effort to maintain organizational balance in HIV/AIDS prevention efforts. Elements of transformational leadership, such as idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individual consideration, must be consistently maintained to maintain organizational balance. A transformational leader must be able to inspire and result in more innovative organizational performance and commitment to achieving organizational goals.

Keywords: Transformational Leadership, organizational balance, Proactive personality, Bureaucratic Behavior, HIV/AIDS Prevention.

1. INTRODUCTION

The implementation of the wheels of government is very important in making public policies and implementing a government system that includes the system of government administration and the relationship of authorities, functions, and duties of an institution to the realization of a good public policy that can meet the needs of the community. This is consistent with Gerston's (2002) assertion that public policies are developed and implemented at all levels of government, so policymakers' responsibilities will differ depending on their authority. This is also in line with the opinion of George C. Edwards III and Ira Sharkansky in Suwitri,(2008) that public policy is a government action in the form of government programs to achieve goals or objectives.

To bring the government closer to the community and reflect the democratization process by accommodating the interests and aspirations of the community, it is necessary to consider various aspects in making a policy because the public policy process is complicated and involves the interests of the community. In solving government problems, apart from the need for a policy, policymakers are also needed who can face the times and environmental demands, so leaders who are ready to face the demands of these changes are needed.

Transformational leadership is needed to meet the challenges of the times and bring about change in an organization. To meet the challenges of the times and accommodate the interests of the community in the prevention of HIV/AIDS, the Aids Prevention Commission was formed based on Presidential Regulation No. 75 of 2006. HIV/AIDS remains the leading cause of death and decreased productivity among the productive age group. The high incidence of HIV/AIDS in an area is the basis for prevention efforts.

This was stated in an independent commission report entitled "Redefining AIDS in Asia: Crafting an Effective Response," where the AIDS problem in Asia occurs in the 15–44 year age group. (Report of the AIDS Commission in Asia, 2015). The need to improve the quality of education about HIV is also explained by Rui Li (2015) to overcome students' misconceptions and attitudes towards the disease. Luana (2015) et al. also mentioned the importance of monitoring adolescents as a follow-up effort in tackling HIV/AIDS. Badariah (2015) also conveyed the same thing about adolescents' understanding of HIV/AIDS transmission that can be transmitted through other people's body fluids, which will have a tremendous impact on the quality of life of adolescents.

To maintain and improve the health of the community to the greatest extent possible, the government and the community must carry out the mandate of Health Law No. 36 of 2009. It is mandated in Presidential Regulation No. 75 of 2006 that it is necessary to increase efforts to control HIV and AIDS. AIDS (Acquired Immunodeficiency Syndrome) throughout Indonesia. Efforts to prevent HIV/AIDS can be carried out together with the public and private sectors; this is in line with what was conveyed by Collin (2016), who said that the social responsibility of public companies makes an invaluable contribution to reducing the negative effects of HIV/AIDS. Likewise, the importance of advocacy to local governments and education authorities, as well as school management, is the key to the success of HIV prevention programs in schools, as stated by Pohan et al. (2011).

Therefore, it is necessary to improve services to the community in an effort to prevent HIV/AIDS. According to Mattaboge (2015) in his journal, the inability of marginalized communities to access health services, as well as the government's poor provision of health services, impede HIV/AIDS prevention efforts, such as a lack of access to information about prevention, early diagnosis, and treatment. Hsi-hsien Wei (2016) also mentioned in a case report the need for services for clinical vigilance in anticipating vertical HIV transmission.

With the increasing problem of HIV/AIDS, leaders are needed who are able to bring about changes in HIV/AIDS prevention efforts so that development goals are achieved, namely the realization of optimal health degrees.

2. METHODOLOGY

Data analysis was carried out using qualitative methods, with a descriptive-analytical approach used to analyze the literature. Secondary data retrieval was carried out using a scientific search method approach and a literature study. Scientific searches are based on data needs that can be obtained from government agencies and online data searches. The literature study was conducted to interpret and describe the data that can support this article.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Traits and Dimensions of Transformational Leadership

The environment has the power to force organizations to make changes, and almost every organization has to adapt to a multicultural environment. Michel Beer (2002) states that the concept of change is choosing a different action than before; it is the difference that produces a change.

Change in an organization is important because organizational change is a significant progress process. If an organization delays change, it is facing a setback process. Although not all changes lead to better conditions, it is necessary to direct a positive change.

The organizational change aims to increase the effectiveness of the organization and move it in a better direction. Every organization has a target to make changes according to the needs and goals of the organization.

The theory put forward by Van Meter and Van Horn (1975: 462) as a model of the policy implementation process, by suggesting six variables that form the bond between policy and achievement (six variables that shape the linkage between policy and performance), and the importance of implementation procedures, pays attention to the concepts of change, control, and compliance. Six Van Meter and Van Horn variables regarding implementation include (1) standards and policy objectives; (2) resources; (3) communication; (4) inter-organizational and inauguration activities; (5) characteristics of implementing agents; (6) social, economic, and political conditions; as well as the character of the implementer.

To achieve organizational change, an organization needs a strong and qualified leader. According to Robbin organizational change, an organization needs a strong and qualified leader. According to Robbins (2015, leadership is the ability to influence a group to achieve a set vision or goal. According to this theory, a leader is expected to communicate the vision to be achieved by the organization so that the vision of the organization can be built.

This is also in line with the opinion of Robert D. Stuart (2002), who states that a leader can influence, give instructions, and determine individuals to achieve the vision or goals of the organization.

Because of the importance of the role of a public administrator or a leader, a supportive attitude or behavior is needed in the implementation of an organization.

The personality traits that are relevant to the organization based on Stephen J. Robbins's organizational behavior (2015) are:

- Core self-evaluation (CSE)

In terms of job satisfaction, individuals who have a positive core self-evaluation perform better, set more ambitious goals, are more committed to their goals, and last longer in an effort to achieve them.

- Self-monitoring

Individuals who have high self-control score better on performance ratings, are more likely to emerge as leaders, and show less commitment to the organization.

-Personality that is proactive

Individuals who have a proactive personality have the initiative to improve a condition. They are able to identify opportunities, show initiative, take action, and persist until meaningful change occurs.

A transformational leader must be able to inspire his followers to go beyond their own interests in order to influence them (Robbins, 2015). Transformational leaders are able to produce superior organizational performance and increase the effectiveness of their followers, so that their followers tend to be ambitious and agree with the strategic goals of the organization. However, even though a transformational leader has a positive performance and response to the policy, it must be supported by the commitment of the implementer to achieve the policy objectives. The leadership's response and commitment are in line with Dawuni's research (2008) in "The Gendered Face of HIV/AIDS: The Move Toward Policy Implementation in Ghana," which states that the government of Ghana established a National STDs and AIDS Control Program under the Ministry of Health.

In Indonesia, the role of the leader is in inspiring and producing performance, especially in efforts to fight HIV/AIDS, as outlined by Nafsiah, 2006, in a journal entitled "Indonesia Fighting a Rising Tide: The Response to AIDS in East Asia." In his research, he found several obstacles related to the fight against HIV/AIDS in Indonesia. First, the breadth and diversity of Indonesia's territory Second, the growing sex industry and the lack of willingness to use condoms Third, obstacles in responding to injecting drugs Fourth, there is an inconsistency between knowledge and behavior. Fifth, poverty. Sixth, the limited capacity of the health system Seventh, there is stigma and discrimination. Eighth, gender inequality. Ninth, group rejection is under control with the use of condoms. The conclusion of this study states that many things related to the HIV/AIDS war depend on leaders at all levels, the level of involvement of the local community in fighting HIV/AIDS, and the effectiveness of the services provided to those in need. (Nafsiah Mboi and Smith, 2006)

The four dimensions of transformational leadership proposed by Bass and Avolio (1994) are:

1. The first dimension is idealized influence (ideal influence).

This means that every word and deed a leader does must be appropriate because it will be a role model for his followers. In Indonesian culture, this is known by the principle of "Ing ngarso sung tulodo." Leaders like this are usually highly admired, respected, and trusted by their followers.

2. The second dimension is inspirational motivation. In this dimension, a leader is able to show high commitment to the vision of the organization so that they are able to clearly articulate expectations for the performance of their subordinates and create enthusiasm for the team within the organization.

3. The third dimension is called "intellectual stimulation." A leader in this dimension must be able to generate creative ideas in order to create an innovation or be a problem solver in order to solve organizational problems.

4. The fourth dimension is individualized consideration.

Leaders in this fourth dimension must have the ability to listen and pay attention to the aspirations of their subordinates for the career development of their subordinates, which are called human skills.

The four dimensions proposed by Bass and Avolio (1994) are an energy capable of maintaining an organization's balance in dealing with all situations if it is consistently maintained. To keep an organization running smoothly, leaders must be able to make decisions. Empirical studies of decision-making and planning in organizations, known as the theory of decision-making behavior (Simon, 1947; Frank Fisher, 2015: 62), state that decision-making in fact does not follow a specific sequence of stages, and this is useful as an ideal type of planning and decision-making. Rational decision. Meanwhile, according to rational theory, every decision must be based on a comprehensive analysis of the problem and objectives, followed by a thorough collection and analysis of information, and the search for the best alternative to achieve the goal (Noviana, 2009). However, even though a number of leaders are involved in controlling or shaping the agenda, most of the variables and mechanisms that affect agenda setting are outside the direct control of the leadership. Although the agenda-setting mechanism does not determine how related policies are designed and implemented, it will have an impact on policy implementation.

Factors influencing policy-making behavior.

Policy implementation is a very important aspect of the entire policy process, because apart from being related to the mechanism for elaborating decisions, it also involves decisions about who gets what and who gets what in a policy related to conflict issues.

These factors are as follows (Nigro, F.A., and Nigro, L.G., Modern Public Administration, New York: Harper & Row Publishers, 5th ed., 1980: 207):

a) There are external pressures.

Often public officials have to make decisions because of external pressures. One of the policy making is based on rational assumptions (that is, policy makers must consider alternatives to be selected based on a rational assessment), but the processes and procedures for making policies cannot be separated from the real world, so that external pressures also influence the decision-making process. The decision-making process. This pressure can come from superiors or from other institutions.

b) The influence of old habits (conservatism).

The old habits of the organization tend to be followed by public officials even though for example these decisions have been criticized as wrong and need to be changed. These old habits are often inherited by new public officials and they are often reluctant to openly criticize or blame the old habits that have been applied or carried out by their predecessors.

c) The influence of personal traits.

Various kinds of decisions made by policy makers have a lot of influence on their personal characteristics. For example, in the process of accepting/appointing a new official, the personal characteristics of the decision maker often play a major role.

d) The influence of past circumstances.

Past experience sometimes influences policy making. For example, people often make decisions not to delegate some of their authority and responsibility to others because they are afraid that the delegated authority and responsibility will be misused.

The Direct Effect of Transformational Leadership on HIV/AIDS Prevention

A strong leader is needed by an organization to support the vision to be achieved. Transformational leaders are very effective because they are able to inspire and motivate their followers to do better. The opinion of a management expert states that there are seven characteristics of transformational leaders, namely: being able to be an agent of change; being brave; empowering others; being driven by values; being a lifelong learner; being able to overcome the complexity of problems; and having visionary abilities. A leader who is able to overcome problems in HIV/AIDS prevention efforts is a leader who is truly competent in his field. The expected changes must be based on arguments and a solid foundation in the prevention of HIV/AIDS, not just changes. The arguments presented by a transformational leader are accompanied by courage, so that they are able to change attitudes and take risks in HIV/AIDS prevention efforts. Transformational leaders are people who are not afraid of failure, because in failure there is learning.

A transformational leader maintains an open attitude and encourages his subordinates to innovate and correct all errors in the organization, resulting in reciprocal behavior toward subordinates. The ability of a public administrator to analyze policies shows that there is a synergy between understanding policy analysis, understanding the developing HIV/AIDS phenomenon, and the carrying capacity of its ability to solve a concrete HIV/AIDS problem.

However, all phenomena regarding transformational leaders are also inseparable from the concept of power. Understanding how much influence transformational leaders have in the policy process means we understand the concept of power as well as how power is used. Power can be categorized based on personal

wealth, personality, level of or access to knowledge, or authority, but it is closely related to the organization and structure in which these individual actors work and live. Understanding this concept will affect the performance of transformational leaders, both in terms of positive and negative influences, all depending on how well they understand the concept.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The administration of government is closely related to public policy and will be effective if accompanied by a healthy bureaucracy. In order to bring the government closer to the people in an effort to reflect the process of democratization by accommodating the interests and aspirations of the people, it is necessary to consider various aspects when making a policy because the public policy process is a complicated and complex process that involves the interests of the community. Transformational leadership is needed to meet the challenges of the times and bring about change in an organization. In an effort to face the challenges of the times and accommodate the interests of the community for the prevention of HIV/AIDS, it is necessary to have leaders who are able to bring about changes in efforts to prevent HIV/AIDS so that development goals are achieved, namely the realization of optimal health status. A transformational leader is a leader who is able to inspire his followers to go beyond their own interests and has the ability to influence their followers. Transformational leaders are able to produce superior organizational performance and increase the effectiveness of their followers, so that their followers tend to be ambitious and agree with the strategic goals of the organization. A leader who is able to overcome problems in efforts to prevent HIV/AIDS is a leader who is truly competent in his field. The expected changes must be based on arguments and a solid foundation in efforts to prevent HIV/AIDS, not just change.

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